

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF UNIVERSAL
PHARMACY AND BIO SCIENCES****IMPACT FACTOR 4.018*******ICV 6.16*******Pharmaceutical Sciences****Research Article.....!!!****A STUDY ON DRUG PRESCRIBING PATTERN AND DISEASE PATTERN OF
OUTPATIENTS VISITING OPHTHALMOLOGY DEPARTMENT IN A RURAL
TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL**Mr. Ravindra B.N¹, Dr Prolay Paul^{2*}, Dr Pudota Mary Pravallika³Dr Praveen P⁴, Dr H.T. Venkate Gowda.⁵

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ABSTRACT**KEYWORDS:**

Ophthalmology, Ocular disease, Optometry, Conjunctivitis.

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Ophthalmology may be defined as the branch of medical sciences dealing with the anatomy, functions, and disease of eye. Many eye diseases don't have any early warning signs of symptoms but, a dilated exam can detect eye diseases in their preliminary stages before vision loss occurs. The foremost common ocular diseases are Cataract, Glaucoma, Conjunctivitis, Corneal ulcers, Blepharitis, Refractive errors, and Pterygium. The study was a Prospective Observational Study. Considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria subject was enrolled to the study after procuring the written consent individually. The suitably designed data collection form was used to collect all the necessary information. The participants were explained well about the study before taking their data and cleared all their doubt about the study. During the study a total no. of 174 prescriptions were analyzed in ophthalmology OPD out of these no. of drugs per prescription varied from 0-8 the prescription containing one drug are 80, two drugs are 654, and we found that most of the drugs prescribed are antibiotics 117 followed by NSAIDS 57, and Our results show that a total no. of 174 prescriptions were diagnosed in OPD among these patients, maximum was diagnosed with Conjunctivitis 45 followed by dry eyes 18.

INTRODUCTION:

Ophthalmology may be defined as the branch of medical sciences dealing with the anatomy, functions, and disease of eye. At the age of 40's you most likely notice that your vision is changing, these changes are a standard part of aging. But as the age increases, the risk of developing eye diseases also increases. Many eye diseases don't have any early warning signs of symptoms but, a dilated exam can detect eye diseases in their preliminary stages before vision loss occurs so, everyone at the age of 50's is usually recommended to go to eye care professionals for a comprehensive dilated eye exam. Thus, the appropriate medication or treatment is required for proper eye care.¹ However, the tendency of ocular diseases varies worldwide and also influenced by racial, geographic, socio-economic, and cultural factors. The foremost common ocular diseases are Cataract, Glaucoma, Conjunctivitis, Corneal ulcers, Blepharitis, Refractive errors, and Pterygium. The foremost common eye diseases seen among patients attending ophthalmic outreach services in an exceedingly geographical region in Ethiopia were Conjunctivitis, Cataract, Presbyopia, Refractive errors, and Blepharitis. From Benin City (Nigeria) reported Refractive errors, Conjunctivitis, Cataract, and Glaucoma to be the common eye diseases.² Optimum management of ocular disease has huge impact in prevention of loss of vision in patients plagued by eye problems. Appropriate management of those patients reduces the burden of the ocular health problems. Drug utilization pattern must be evaluated regularly to extend therapeutic efficacy, decrease adverse effects and also to assess whether drug therapy is rational or not. Within the past only few studies were available about drug use pattern in ophthalmology in India. Therefore, the current study was conducted to study the drug use in ophthalmology and to assess its rationality with WHO core drug prescribing indicator.⁴

Drug utilization research was defined by World Health Organization (WHO) in 1977 as the marketing, distribution, prescription, and use of medication in a society, with special emphasis on the resulting medical, social and economic consequences. The ultimate goal of drug utilization research must be to assess whether drug therapy is rational or not. To achieve this goal, methods for auditing drug therapy towards rationality are necessary. Regular audit of prescriptions and providing the feedback to physicians can improve their performance and increase the effectiveness and safety of treatment provided.⁵ Drug utilization studies provide a pharmacoeconomic basis for building evidence-based health-care decisions. In ophthalmology practice, use of rational drugs plays an essential role in reducing the ocular disease burden.⁶

Drug utilization pattern has to be studied carefully to reinforce therapeutic efficacy, decrease side effects and also to judge the rationality of drug prescription. Previously, only some studies were conducted to check drug use pattern in ophthalmology in India. Therefore, this study was conducted to review the

drug use in ophthalmology.⁷The indiscriminating utilization of topical antibiotics and NSAID drugs cause histological and structural changes in conjunctiva with the aim of improving drugs therapeutic efficacy, delay development of resistance, and minimize ADE must to be assessed occasionally. Consequently, this study was undertaken with the aim to look at drug utilization and prescribing practices of ophthalmology.³ In ophthalmology practice, rational use of drugs plays a significant role in decreasing the ocular disease burden of the country. Though majority of those earlier studies considered WHO suggested prescribing indicators; just one study provided information regarding the ocular disorder from which the patients were suffering.⁸

OBJECTIVES:**PRIMARY OBJECTIVE:**

To study the drug prescribing pattern and disease pattern in patients visiting ophthalmology department at Adichunchanagiri Hospital and Research Centre (AH&RC), B.G Nagara, Mandya.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES:

To study percentage of drugs prescribed from essential medicine list (EML).

STUDY CRITERIA:**Inclusion criteria:**

All patients who were willing to participate after getting the written informed consent & attending the ophthalmology department of the hospital was included in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

Those patients who are not willing to participate in the study.

METHODOLOGY

The study was a Prospective Observational Study. The study was carried out over a period of 6 months from October 2019- April 2020. The study was approved by Institutional Ethical Committee, AH&RC, B G Nagara, (No; AIM/IEC/200/2019-20) Annexure No-1. Considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria subject was enrolled to the study after procuring the written consent individually. The suitably designed data collection form was used to collect all the necessary information. The participants were explained well about the study before taking their data and cleared all their doubt about the study. The collected data was transcript into excel spread sheet for calculation. Suitable statistical method was used for the analysis of the data obtained. The data was entered in Microsoft excel. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS V.22. Descriptive statistical method including frequency, mean, mode & median was determined for the socio demographic details.

RESULTS:**1. Socio- demographic characteristics of the participants in ophthalmic outpatients. (N= 174)**

A total of 174 prescriptions were analyzed. The mean age of the subjects was 39.31 years (SD29.90) out of these male patients were 57.5% and female patients were 42.5%. And The study result showed that 40 patients of 1-20years of age 54 patients are 21-40years of age,51 patients are from 41-60 years of age 29 patients are from 60 and greater years of age.

TABLE 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants in ophthalmic outpatients.

Age group	Number of Participants	Percentage
1-20	40	22.9
21-40	54	31.0
41-60	51	29.3
60≥	29	16.8
Sex		
Male	100	57.5
Female	74	42.5

Mean age: 39.31 SD ± 29.90 (N= 174)

2. No. of drugs prescribed per prescriptions of Ophthalmic Outpatients.

During this study a total no. of 174 prescriptions were analyzed. Out of these the no. of prescription varied from 0-8. There were no drugs prescribed in 12 prescriptions. Each prescription was analyzed and statics analysis showed that Prescription containing 1-2 drugs was found to be 77%, 3-4 drugs were 14.3%, 5-6 drugs were 0.11.

TABLE 2: No. of drugs prescribed per prescriptions of Ophthalmic Outpatients.

PRESCRIPTION CONTAINING NUMBER OF DRUGS	NUMBER OF PRESCRIPTIONS	NUMBER OF PRESCRIPTION (%)
.00	12	6.9
1-2	134	77.0
3-4	25	14.3
5-6	2	0.11
7-8	1	0.057

3. No. of dosage forms prescribed per prescription of Ophthalmic Outpatients.

Out of 174 prescriptions 162 prescriptions were prescribed with the different dosage forms. The maximum no. of dosage forms prescribed per prescription is 3 and minimum no. of dosage form prescribed per prescription is 1. Single dosage form of drug was prescribed in 64.8% patients; 2 dosage forms of drugs were prescribed in 30.24% prescriptions and 3 dosage forms of drugs were prescribed in 4.96% prescriptions.

TABLE 3:-No. of dosage forms prescribed per prescription of Ophthalmic Outpatients.

NO OF DOSAGE FORMS PRESCRIBED PER PRESCRIPTIONS	NO. OF PRESCRIPTIONS	PERCENT (%)
1	105	64.8
2	49	30.24
3	8	4.96
Total	162	100

4. Distribution of diseases:

Statistics analysis shows that out of 174 prescription 25.9% patients were diagnosed with conjunctivitis, 10.3% patients were diagnosed with dry eyes, and 9.8% patients were diagnosed with refractive errors.

Table 4:- Distribution Of Diseases

Ocular Diseases	No. Of Prescriptions	Percent
Conjunctivitis	45	25.9
Dry Eyes	18	10.3
Refractive Errors	17	9.8
Allergy	15	8.6
Pterygium	12	6.9
Blepharitis	8	4.6
Episcleritis	5	2.9
Infection	5	2.9
Corneal Ulcer	4	2.3
Trauma	4	2.3
Physical Injury	4	2.3
Insect Bite	4	2.3
Trauma With Mild Conjestion	3	1.7
Internal Hardeluem+Orbital Celulitis	3	1.7
Lacrimial Duct Distortion	3	1.7
Glucoma	2	1.1

Macular Edema	2	1.1
Diabetic Retinopathy	2	1.1
Grade 2 Hyperactive Retinopathy	2	1.1
Chemical Injury	2	1.1
Myopic Fundus	1	.6
Nadacranial Dust Distortion	1	.6
Papilloma Of Caruncle	1	.6
Age Related Macular Degeneration	1	.6
Bell's Palsy And Logophthalmar	1	.6
Cataract	1	.6
Chalazion	1	.6
Corneal Sensation With Cyst	1	.6
Keratitis With Staphyloma	1	.6
Left Eye External Hardeleoum	1	.6
Meibomitis	1	.6
Foreign Body Sensation	1	.6
Pseudophil Eyes	1	.6
Re Internal Hardeleum	1	.6
Total	174	100.0

5. Classes of drugs prescribed in ophthalmology outpatients

A total of 174 prescriptions were collected among which most of them were antibiotics, a total no. of 40.4% antibiotics were prescribed followed by Anti-inflammatory 7%, Cycloplegics 4.8%, Anti-glaucoma 0.7%, Antihistamines 2.8%, NSAIDS 19.7%, Vitamins 3.1%, Artificial tears 21.5%.

TABLE 5:-Classes of drugs prescribed in ophthalmology outpatients

CLASS OF A DRUG	NO. OF DRUGS	PERCENT
Antibiotics	117	40.4%
Anti-inflammatory	20	7%
Cycloplegics	14	4.8%
Anti-glaucoma	2	0.7%
Antihistamines	8	2.8%
NSAID's	57	19.7%
Vitamins	9	3.1%
Artificial tears	62	21.5%
TOTAL	289	100%

6. Drug core indicators:

Total no. of prescriptions	174
Average no. of drugs per prescription	1.78
Total no. of drug prescribed	289
No. of antibiotics prescribed	117
No. of drugs from WHO EML	73
No. of injection prescribed	00

DISCUSSION:

A total of 174 outpatients from the study site were enrolled in the study by considering study criteria the present study was conducted in Ophthalmology Department of Adichunchanagiri Hospital and Research Centre Gender distribution of patients is enrolled in the study. A total no. of 174 prescriptions was analyzed in the OPD ophthalmology department. The result showed that, out of 174 patients from the OPD majority of them are male 100(57.5%) and female patients were 74(43.5%). A lower no. of drug per prescription indicates less chance of drug interaction, less chances of ADR and better compliance, indirectly it is also indicating more chances of correct diagnosis. Average no. of drug per prescription is an important index as it tends to measure the Polypharmacy. During the study a total no. of 174 prescriptions were analyzed in ophthalmology OPD out of these no. of drugs per prescription varied from 0-8 the prescription containing one drug are 80, two drugs are 654, three drugs are 18, four drugs are 7, five drugs are 1, six drugs are 1, and eight drugs are 1. The result showed that average no. of 1.78 drugs is prescribed in ophthalmology outpatient department. Our study was similar to Neelkant reddy patil et.al., there study shows that no. of prescription varied from 1-6 prescription containing one drug are 21, two drug are 100, three drug are 59, four drug are 21, five drug are 2 and six are 2 and average no. of drugs per prescription are 2.¹ Average should always maintain low as possible to reduce adverse effect, bacterial resistance level and patient medication cost range. It shows degree of Polypharmacy and average value ranges from 1.6 to 1.8%. The prescribing error should be low by maintaining the average number and the appropriate use of drugs and drug prescribing pattern will increase the patient benefits in several aspect and also health of public. In our study for the analysis of 174 OPD prescriptions we found the result that most of the drugs prescribed are antibiotics 117 followed by NSAIDS 57, followed by anti-inflammatory 20, cycloplegics 14, antihistamines 8, vitamins 9 and anti-glaucoma 2 at last artificial tears were prescribed 62 times. While comparing our results to RajeshKumar suman et.al. found to be similar to our study where in their study antibiotics were in the 14.69%, antiviral was 4.12%, antihistamine are 49.14% steroids were 11.98% followed by anti-inflammatory are in 6.04% and at last artificial tears were in 22.23%.⁹ Eye drops most commonly

prescribed dosage form for ophthalmology treatment mainly all types of dosage groups such as antibiotic, steroids, artificial tear and anti-glaucoma drugs are mainly prescribed in drops form for eye diseases. NSAIDs and vitamins mainly prescribed in tablet form and antibiotic are mainly prescribed in ointment and gel form, vitamins are prescribed in capsules or tablet form.

CONCLUSION:

Majority of all the prescriptions in our study contains all these essential prerequisites. Out of 289 drugs prescribed from OPD (25%) of the drugs were prescribed from the WHOEML. During the study a total no. of 174 prescriptions were analyzed in ophthalmology OPD out of these no. of drugs per prescription varied from 0-8 the prescription containing one drug are 80, two drugs are 654, three drugs are 18, four drugs are 7, five drugs are 1, six drugs are 1, and eight drugs are 1. The result showed that average no. of 1.78 drugs are prescribed in ophthalmology outpatient department. These above value shows poly pharmacy was less. In this study, 6 different types of dosage form are prescribed in the ophthalmology OPD. The result showed that a total no. of 174 prescriptions are collected out of these most of them are eye drops 202, followed by tablets 61, eye ointments were 22 capsules 2 syrups 1 and shampoo 1. Our results show that a total no. of 174 prescriptions were diagnosed in OPD among these patients, maximum was diagnosed with Conjunctivitis 45 followed by dry eyes 18 allergy 15 Pterygium 12 and Blepharitis 8 etc. In our study for the analysis of 174 OPD prescriptions we found the result that most of the drugs prescribed are antibiotics 117 followed by NSAIDS 57, followed by anti-inflammatory 20, cycloplegics 14, antihistamines 8, vitamins 9 and anti-glaucoma 2 at last artificial tears were prescribed 62 times. The most important parameters/essential prerequisites which are mandatory prescription are route of administration, duration of therapy and frequency of administration. Majority of all the prescriptions in our study contains all these essential prerequisites. Out of 289 drugs prescribed from OPD (25%) of the drugs were prescribed from the WHOEML. The prescribing pattern observed in the current study was knowledge-based and in accordance with the accepted patterns of treatment of ocular diseases, but the study showed ample scope for improvement in encouraging the ophthalmologists to prescribe by generic name and selection of essential drugs from WHOEML/NEDL/NFI. The study revealed that prescription writing errors were minimum.

ABBREVIATIONS:

WHO EML - world health organization essential medicine list

NSAID - Non steroidal anti inflammatory drugs.

ADE - Adverse drug event

ADR - Adverse drug reaction

NEDL - National Essential Diagnostic List

REFERENCE:

1. Neelkant Reddy Patil*, Shetty Sai Shishir, Sankeerthana. A, Rammya Sajjan, Sri Sai Kasyap.Ch. A Study On Drug Utilization Among Ambulatory Patients Visiting Department Of Ophthalmology At A Tertiary Care Hospital International Journal Of Pharmacy And Pharmaceutical Research August 2019 Vol.:16, Issue:1.
2. Ali Ab. Pattern of Eye Diseases at Tertiary Eye Hospital in Sudan (Makah Eye Hospital, Khartoum). Al-Basar International Journal of Ophthalmology. 2015 Jan 1;3(1):15.
3. Rawah Ma, Alkhayri Mm, Alomari Ma, Almalki Rk, Alyahya Fh, Alotaibi Fa, Meriky Lh, Alawami Ss, Alomari Ma, Jan Rm, Banjar Am. Drug Prescription In Ophthalmology. The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine. 2017 Oct 1;69(7):2856-9.
4. Prajapati V, Yadav Ak. Drug Use In Ophthalmology Out-Patient Department: A Prospective Study At A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital. Indian Journal Of Pharmacy Practice. 2012;5(2).
5. Rathnakar Up, Kamath A, Gupta K, Gupta A, Naushad Sg, Kotekar Mf, Shenoy V. A Descriptive Study Of Drug Utilization In Outpatients Of Ophthalmology Department Of A University Teaching Hospital In Southern India. Journal Of Clinical And Biomedical Sciences. 2014 Dec 31;4(4):346-8.
6. Banerjee I, Bhadury T, Sengupta T, Roy D. Drug Utilization Study In Ophthalmology Outpatient Department Of A Medical College In India. Annals Of Medical And Health Sciences Research. 2014;4(4):667-70.
7. Slathia A, Gupta V, Nanda R, Mahajan P. Drug Utilization Pattern In Ophthalmology: A Observational And Cross-Sectional Study. International Journal Of Scientific Study. 2017 Aug 1;5(5):63-5.
8. Dhali D, Halder U, Santra R, Biswas M. Drug Utilization Study In Outpatient Ophthalmology Department Of A Tertiary Care Hospital In West Bengal. In Indian Journal Of Pharmacology 2014 Dec 1 (Vol. 46, Pp. S55-S56).
9. Suman Rk, Gore Vs, Mohanty Ir, Israni N, Deshmukh Ya. Drug Utilization Patterns Of Drugs Used In Ophthalmology Out-Patients Department At Tertiary Care Hospital.
10. World Health Organization. World Health Organization Model List Of Essential Medicines: 21st List 2019. World Health Organization; 2019.